

Interview - DAFNI DINI project

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

This document describes an interview undertaken as part of the context setting work. You can find a synthesis of all other interviews here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15102198>

Interview: DAFNI DINI project

Meeting date: 21/02/2025

We spoke to the Data Engineering Theme Lead and DAFNI Programme Lead and Project Delivery Manager who are both based within Scientific Computing at the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC). They work with teams who are developing and maintaining digital research infrastructures or working within data/digital domains.

DAFNI (Data & Analytics Facility for National Infrastructure) is a computing platform which aims to support advanced research into national infrastructure. The DAFNI programme aims to improve the efficiency, reliability, and sustainability of infrastructure through better sharing and use of data, exploitation of simulation and optimization techniques, and engagement with stakeholders through visualisation.

We met on Friday 21st February 2025 to discuss their pilot project (funded via the same call as ours) and their experience in user centred design more generally. This document provides a summary of the discussion.

In the Scientific Computing department, there are four main areas that do work relevant to this project. We were provided an overview as follows:

- **Data engineering theme**
- **DAFNI**

- DAFNI is a digital research infrastructure that has been working on infrastructure systems engineering, such as water distribution, energy supply, transport networks.
- Types of users: Civil engineers, environmental scientists - some cross over with the Environmental Data Service (specifically the CEDA Archive)
- DAFNI has a more user friendly front-end (compared to JASMIN which is largely command line based). It focuses on data management and workflow composition - so users don't need to know linux/command line.
- Often the software design ends up being back-end first and is not always designed with users' needs as a priority. No systematic approach to user-centred design.
- DAFNI allows researchers to scale and integrate their computational models to explore the social and environmental impacts of changes in infrastructure with much greater coverage and detail, and to deposit, share and use data collected in research projects and generated in models.
- DAFNI provides systems to support building of digital twin workflows and can provide support with applying data standards and metadata
- **Wider STFC (e.g. ISIS/Diamond) data management**
- **DRI programme for physical sciences**
- **Software engineering theme** - not started yet
 - The software engineering theme will (aims to) support software engineering across the Scientific Computing Department (the department running DAFNI), promote EDI for software engineering, develop communities of interest across different areas, and provide specialised expertise.

We particularly wanted to speak about the DAFNI Data Infrastructure for National Infrastructure (DINI) project (funded by the same pilot funding as our project), and understand how co-creation and user centred activities have been led.

The DINI project examines what is needed to deliver data and good research with impact for government, industry and the public at large. The DAFNI DINI project focuses on the requirements and impact of supporting sharing and analysis of data across National Infrastructure systems, with a focus on energy, water and transport, and the related natural, built and social and economic environment.

To gather evidence for the project, research partners were commissioned to undertake some of the work. This was achieved via:

- Sandpit projects - a mechanism for getting together a range of experts who wouldn't usually work together, creating a proposal and successful bids receive funding to do the work
- Champions - a closed funded opportunity as a mechanism to target community experts
- Workshops - to speak with academia, government and industry to understand the different opportunities and barriers in data sharing

The findings from this work is being synthesised into a report and will be shared with the Department of Science, Innovation and Technology at the start of April 2025.

Shared challenges identified:

- Staffing - not enough staff resource due to retention issues and recruitment freeze
 - DINI solution: outsourcing a lot of the project work to research partners
 - DINI solution: Outsourcing responsibility to individuals for setting up contracts with their institutions and STFC (rather than Katie doing this for all)
 - Potential solution: make use of the STEM futures programme - requires organisations sign an agreement, then you can easily post opportunities/send staff on secondment to do projects where resources are needed across the programme
- Short time scale for funding (and compressed further due to delays)
 - No real solution, we agreed that it is exacerbated alongside staffing challenges.
- Vastness of evidence collected that needs synthesising

Key points from our discussion

- The DAFNI team regularly show prototypes to users and get feedback as standard practice, but they don't have a philosophy behind this or a systematic user-centred design focussed approach.
- Similar staffing challenges exacerbated by short funding timescales, delayed funding period, and recruitment freezes
- Creative solutions to the staffing challenges included: outsourcing work via sub projects (sandpit events), champions, workshops.
- Brian was very complimentary about our draft toolkit - and the wider team are keen to see how it develops in the future

Areas for possible future collaborations

Future project across teams about implementing user centred design practices in our teams

Sharing good practice